

Data Management in Local Disaster Risk Reduction-Climate Change Adaptation in the Philippines: Scenarios and Strategies

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Abstract. Within the administrative structure of the Philippine government, local government units (LGUs) play a crucial role as frontline agencies for disaster risk reduction - climate change adaptation (DRR-CCA). However, many LGUs continue to struggle with data management, an essential component of effective DRR-CCA interventions. This study explores this challenge by examining emerging trends and issues in the local DRR-CCA data management landscape through a futures thinking lens, adding value to the existing body of knowledge by looking into a myriad of factors that affect data management for local DRR-CCA and by systematically imagining and describing potential future scenarios. Drawing from literature reviews and key informant interviews, the study identifies five key driving forces—or influential factors—that affect local DRR-CCA data management: institutional capacity, level of digital technology diffusion, standards for data management, the digital divide, and emerging technologies. These factors served as the foundation for developing potential future scenarios, including a preferred scenario, along with corresponding goals and strategies for the year 2050 that can guide future institutional and policy reforms. These outputs were validated through consultations with scholars and practitioners via email interviews.

Keywords: disaster risk reduction - climate change adaptation (DRR-CCA), local government units, data management, information and communication technologies (ICT), futures thinking

Introduction

To effectively implement measures for mitigating disaster risks and adapting to the impacts of climate change, broadly referred to as disaster risk reduction - climate change adaptation (DRR-CCA), it is crucial to gather and utilize sufficient and relevant climate and disaster risk data and information. However, persistent data and information management challenges exist, particularly in developing countries like the Philippines. The lack of risk-related data limits policy development (Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery [GFDRR], 2016a). Centralized data repositories are also often nonexistent, and access can be challenging even when data is available (GFDRR, 2016b). There are also instances where, despite having access to data, it is hard to make sense of what it represents because of the lack of metadata.

In the Philippines, where local government units (LGUs) are at the forefront of DRR-CCA, the climate and disaster-related data localization is also a big challenge, as many LGUs do not have enough resources and capacity to generate their data (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2022a). Another major issue is the lack of focus and resources devoted to DRR-CCA research, which affects the production of updated climate and disaster-related data (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction [UNDRR], 2019). These gaps and challenges particularly hamper the conduct of proper risk assessments, which is a crucial step in the effective development of DRR-CCA measures.

Within the context of local development planning in the Philippines, LGUs are also directed to collect and process substantial data to meet the technical demands for their climate and disaster risk assessments (CDRA) (Domingo & Manejar, 2018). CDRA is the primary tool for mainstreaming DRR-CCA into local governance in the Philippines (Domingo & Manejar, 2018). It entails a six-step assessment process of studying climate and disaster risks and vulnerabilities of different LGUs (Housing and Land Use Regulatory Board [HLURB], 2015). It prepares for their local risk-sensitive spatial and sectoral development plans. However, despite the issuance of comprehensive guidelines by national government agencies, several challenges continue to plague the conduct of CDRA, particularly in data management.

Among primary concerns is the need for more data quality assurance and control at the national level (UNDP, 2022a). This results in inadequate monitoring and tracking of how LGUs conduct their risk assessments, including data collection, processing, and analysis, thus affecting their implementation. Concerning environmental monitoring, LGUs may also often lack direct access to some critical raw data and heavily depend on transmitted and processed information from national agencies with monitoring stations to inform their decisions (Asuncion, 2023). Moreover, infrastructure limitations in the Philippines compound these challenges. For instance, effective environmental monitoring depends on reliable internet connectivity, yet internet access remains unreliable and costly in the Philippines (Mirandilla-Santos, 2021).

This study addresses this problem by exploring emerging trends and challenges in the data management landscape within the local DRR-CCA domain through a futures thinking lens. The rationale behind using a future-oriented framework is to gain a holistic understanding and insights, enabling the systematic identification and development of potential outcomes (Iversen, n.d.). This, in turn, facilitates the formulation of scenarios and strategies that policy-makers and practitioners, both at the national and local level, can use as a reference to strengthen local DRR-CCA data management practices.

Research Gap

A scoping of related literature generally reveals that most studies on data management for local DRR-CCA typically position the subject within the broader context of information and communications technology (ICT) applications/e-governance. This approach stemmed from the integral role of technology in establishing effective data management systems, as various DRR-CCA components require the collection, processing, and analysis of climate and disaster risk data. For example, the recent publications by Roldan (2022) and Asuncion (2023) primarily investigate how ICTs are being applied in DRR-CCA, with their recommendations related to data management mainly focusing on ways to leverage ICTs further. Additionally, there are studies such as those by Li and Fan (2023), Gundran et al. (2023), and Kaur et al. (2022) that delve into the applications of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), augmented reality/virtual reality (AR/VR), and blockchain technology in the context of DRR-CCA. While these studies offer valuable insights, they mainly discuss data management regarding ICT usage. However, it is essential to acknowledge that data management is influenced not only by technological factors but also by social, economic, political, and other factors (Liu, 2022).

Other relevant studies evaluate LGUs' preparedness or readiness, wherein data management often revolves around policy and institutional factors within specific areas or the entire DRR-CCA system. For example, Ner et al. (2022) look into integrating resilience attributes into local disaster management plans in Metro Manila. Their discussion on data management is part of their analysis on the strengths, weaknesses, and gaps of the local disaster risk reduction and management plans (LDRRMPs) they examined, following their analytical framework and methodology. Meanwhile, other studies, such as those by Domingo and Manejar (2018) and Brucal et al. (2020), take a more comprehensive approach, offering recommendations related to data management concerning the administrative and institutional capacity limitations of LGUs. A common limitation across these studies, however, is that they only treat data management challenges as contributors to the level of LGUs' preparedness or readiness concerning DRR-CCA without a nuanced exploration of how to address data management-related issues in greater detail.

Therefore, this study's major contribution is its focus on data management for local DRR-CCA instead of considering it solely as a component within the broader context of how LGUs utilize ICTs or enhance their overall institutional capacities. This approach enables a more holistic examination of the myriad factors influencing data management, facilitating the creation of more precise and strategic recommendations within this domain. UNDP's (2022a) technical report on data governance for DRR-CCA in the Philippines offers similar insights; however, this study adds value by not only examining historical trends and pieces of evidence but also by systematically imagining and describing potential future scenarios using futures thinking and foresight tools.

Methodology

This study generally follows Schwartz's (1996, as cited in Shaw et al., 2019) scenario-building process but has been slightly modified to create a more streamlined and consistent five-step approach. The decision to integrate specific steps is rooted in

methodological considerations, aligning the steps that involve using similar processing and analysis tools for improved coherence in the organization and presentation of the findings. In terms of methodology, this study primarily employs qualitative methods to collect, process, and analyze data from primary sources using key informant interviews (KII) and email interviews, as well as from secondary sources via an extensive review of relevant literature. The subsequent discussions elaborate on the methodologies applied at each step of the modified Schwartz framework.

Scoping

The framework begins with *scoping*, which involves identifying the central issue or decision to be addressed, as proposed by Schwartz. To determine the specific focus of this study, a scoping of related literature on data management, DRR-CCA, climate change, and local governance was conducted. Many of these studies underscore the critical importance of improving data management to enhance the effectiveness of DRR-CCA at the local level. Consequently, the study's focus has been directed towards this crucial aspect. The study is oriented towards the year 2050, 25 years from the expected completion date. This temporal horizon was selected in alignment with the prevailing practices of scientific organizations, including the Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services and Administration (PAGASA), the country's primary meteorological and hydrological services agency (PAGASA, n.d.).

Environmental Scanning

The next step involves *environmental scanning*, where the key forces influencing data management for local DRR-CCA are identified and evaluated, along with their corresponding driving factors. In this regard, a STEEP analysis is employed to guide the collection of relevant data and information. This tool comprehensively recognizes the current and future *social, technological, economic, environmental, and political* factors that impact data management practices within LGUs for DRR-CCA (Lee & Park, 2022; Szigeti et al., 2011). Data and information organized using the STEEP framework are primarily collected through an extensive review of related literature. Additionally, primary data are derived from insights provided by some LGU officials through KIIs. The key informants in this study include five local executive officials/personnel involved in DRR-CCA, with two representing a highly urbanized city (HUC)—Davao City—and three from a component municipality—Tanauan, Leyte. It is important to note that the KIIs serve only as a supplement to the literature reviews. Additionally, instead of presenting the results using the STEEP framework, the environmental scanning results were synthesized and presented as driving forces for more coherent and streamlined discussions. In futures thinking and foresight, driving forces refer to influential factors that can change, shape, or transform a system—in this case, data management for local DRR-CCA (UNDP, 2022b).

For better reliability and external validity, the driving forces are validated through email interviews, using an online questionnaire. An email interview was chosen as a methodology for its efficiency and cost-effectiveness in reaching a broad participant base (Hawkins, 2018), which is an essential aspect in employing futures and foresight techniques. A total of 19 email interview informants participated, with ten (52.63%) representing LGUs and three (15.79%) from national government agencies,

specifically from institutions such as the Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (Phivolcs), National Tax Research Center (NTRC), and the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG). Additionally, there were two project consultants, two informants from non-governmental organizations (NGOs), one from the academe, and one from a private institution.

Prioritization

Subsequently, in the *prioritization* stage, the driving forces are ranked based on their impact and uncertainty. On one hand, impact refers to the extent to which these forces affect the specific area of concern, which, in this study, pertains to data management for local DRR-CCA. On the other hand, uncertainty concerns the likelihood of these forces occurring in the future within a defined horizon. The primary criterion for determining high-impact forces/factors is whether they directly influence the data management performance of LGUs for DRR-CCA without the involvement of any intermediary variables. Regarding uncertainty, forces/factors with unstable trends due to a lack of institutionalized support or policy ecosystem, or those lacking substantial documented data or evidence of natural progression, behavior, or trends, fall under the high uncertainty category.

Scenario Development

The prioritized key and driving forces/factors from the previous step are inputs for the next step—*scenario development*. Based on Schwartz's process framework, two main steps are involved in this stage: selecting scenario logics and fleshing out scenarios. The types of scenarios to be used in the study and their defining characteristics are determined when selecting scenario logics. For this study, Dator's (2009, as cited in Barandon et al., 2021) scenario archetypes—*continued growth, collapse, discipline, and transformation*—are employed. These archetypes' conceptual definitions, as framed by Barandon et al. (2021), are summarized in Table 1. The prioritized driving forces from the previous step, in line with Dator's archetype logics, are used to flesh out the various potential scenarios by the year 2050. These were also validated, refined, and further expanded through the email interviews. Building on the scenario narratives, the researchers distilled a set of desired future conditions by triangulating insights from the KII, scenario validation feedback, and supplementary documentary sources employed in the study. Building on the scenario narratives, the researchers distilled a set of desired future conditions by triangulating insights from the KII, scenario-validation feedback, and supplementary documentary sources employed in the study. Guided by Dator's view that scenario exploration should culminate in articulating a preferred future (Dator, 2009; Bezold, 2009), by Inayatullah's six pillars principle that futures work progresses from mapping alternatives to defining a desired future (Inayatullah, 2008), and by Voros's generic foresight process framework that links exploratory scenarios to a normative vision (Voros, 2003), the researchers synthesized these insights into a single preferred scenario for data management in local DRR-CCA in the Philippines, which served as the benchmark for the goals and strategies.

Table 1
Conceptual Definitions of Dator's Scenario Archetypes

Scenario Archetype	Conceptual Definition
Continued growth	The current development trajectory will continue roughly at the same pace and in the same direction as it has been until now.
Collapse	The current system will regress to a lower development level due to an unforeseen external cause or an internal implosion.
Discipline	Continued growth will be undesirable or unsustainable in the long term, leading society to organize itself around overarching values or principles to exercise constraint.
Transformation	Current forms of behavior, beliefs, or norms will evolve or be replaced by new norms to address some of today's challenges. This is often imagined to be achieved through high-tech developments or spiritual transformation.

Source. Dator, 2009, as cited in Barandon et al., 2021, p. 42

Setting Goals and Strategies

Finally, the last step involves the *setting of goals and strategies*, which broadly covers assessing the implications of the developed scenarios on data management for local DRR-CCA. Following Schwartz's framework, the aim is to ensure that the government, especially LGUs, is resilient or adequately prepared for any potential scenario. In line with this, goals and strategies were also subjected to review by the email interview informants. Note that the results are presented as goals and strategies to align with the local planning system in the Philippines, potentially enabling more seamless integration of the study's findings into the development plans of LGUs (DILG, 2008).

Results and Discussion

Following the environmental scanning results, the driving forces with high impact and uncertainty have been identified and prioritized. The succeeding sections provide an overview of these driving factors, focusing on areas of improvement.

Institutional Capacity

Studies examining LGUs' performance concerning DRR-CCA typically highlight institutional capacity limitations. A law in the Philippines (i.e., Republic Act [RA] 10121) mandates the establishment of a local disaster risk reduction and management office (LDRRMO) and, correspondingly, the creation of permanent positions; however, many LGUs are still unable to comply due to budgetary constraints and difficulties in finding qualified personnel. In a consolidated report, the Commission on Audit (COA, 2022) indicates that nine local governments with LDRRMOs are understaffed, while 54 still do not have LDRRMOs established. This leads local governments to hire temporary, casual, or contractual employees in response (Gabriel et al., 2021). However, potential applicants are discouraged due to low compensation and job insecurity. In an email interview, an informant shared:

LDRRMO employees [are usually] job orders and contractual holding office with no position available, and volunteers are not covered by any

insurance nor granted by hazard pay, considering the high-risk level during disaster or emergencies.

Another contributing factor to this challenge is the restriction imposed by existing laws on local governments regarding budget allocation for personnel services (PS), limiting the budget they can allocate for salaries, wages, and other compensation of regular personnel. Respectively, 1st to 3rd and 4th to 6th income-class LGUs are limited to allocating 45% and 55% of their budget, respectively, for PS.

Even in an HUC like Davao City with a relatively large budget, the KIIs revealed that their designated local disaster office was only a division under the office of their city administrator until 2015. It was not until 2016 that the city established a separate unit. Moreover, their current office still depends heavily on their City Planning Office in conducting their risk assessments and formulating the LDRRMP, suggesting a need to improve the technical capacity of their office in leading the DRR-CCA operations of their city government. This is also reaffirmed by one of the email interview informants, who mentioned observing this trend during their field visits to LGUs as part of their work. They added:

Even the overlaying of risk maps, using geographic information systems (GIS), is more often done by the planning office instead of a local disaster office, which is quite a shame.

This situation may have also resulted, among other factors, from staffing practices prioritizing seniority over qualifications and backgrounds when placing individuals in specific positions, as the discussions from the KIIs suggest.

In the municipality of Tanauan, although they already have a designated local disaster officer, only the head of the office holds an official position with a regular appointment. The remaining staff are either detailed from other offices or contractual employees. In addition to recruitment difficulties, the absence of regular positions leads to high turnover rates, often compelling LGUs to place individuals with limited background and relevant experience in disaster risk reduction management just to meet national policy requirements (Yanquiling, 2020). Additionally, based on the KIIs, capacity development programs and guidelines, whether internally organized or provided by the government or civil society organizations, must be revised to adequately capacitate LGU staff. The overall challenge in capacity development at the local level is compounded by the need for permanent positions, leading to limitations in hiring qualified personnel and high turnover rates (Gabriel et al., 2021). In Mindanao, Minimo (2021) also found that many local governments face major challenges in recruiting and training DRR personnel with technical expertise, primarily due to financial constraints. She noted that even when LGUs are able to train their staff, they often struggle to retain them, not just because of the lack of permanent or better-paying positions, but also because many of these roles require high qualification standards that the trained personnel may not be able to meet.

Concerning climate change adaptation, national policies still do not mandate the creation of an office or unit responsible for developing and implementing climate change-related programs. Consequently, as the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (2020) reports, LGUs do not often have focal persons to handle climate change matters or coordinate related initiatives. These limitations

also hinder LGUs' ability to secure funding for climate change-related activities. For example, there has been a low utilization rate of the People's Survival Fund, a national special fund managed by the Climate Change Commission at the national level, designed to support LGUs' climate change-related programs. In 2020, it was reported that only 172 project proposals from 129 local government and civil society proponents were submitted (Department of Finance [DOF], 2020). Of these, only six were approved because most failed to pass the initial screening due to incomplete documents or ineligibility of proposed activities, caused by their unfamiliarity with pertinent technicalities (Zafra, 2018; Congressional Policy and Budget Research Department [CPBRD], 2019).

These challenges are not exclusive to DRR-CCA but also in other local data management areas. The designation of an information officer or creating an information office/department remains optional across all LGU classes. In Metro Manila cities, the lack of ICT specialists results in limited capacities for developing information systems for effective data management (Asuncion, 2023). In terms of GIS applications, as an example, Lucena's (2018) case study on LGUs in the provincial government of La Union also highlights institutional constraints in the capabilities of the LGU personnel, emphasizing the need for capacity-building and hiring of full-time specialists. To foster a more mature data management culture, addressing these challenges is crucial, as De Castro and De Castro (2022) emphasized, within the context of e-governance. Even at the *barangay* (village) level, Santiago et al. (2020) also underscored officials' need for adequate digital skills to facilitate regular operations and better inform decision-making.

Level of Digital Technology Diffusion

Recognized as the world's social media capital, the Philippines has experienced substantial growth in internet usage and digital adoption (Philippine Digital Justice Initiative [PDJI], 2021). As reported by the World Bank (2020), the number of internet users in the country has more than tripled from 23 million in 2010 to 73 million in 2020. The digital economy's contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP) increased from 7% in 2012 to over 10% in 2018 at constant prices. Despite these achievements, the overall diffusion of digitalization and ICTs in the Philippines still needs to be improved, lagging behind neighboring nations and grappling with various challenges.

Compared to other Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) countries, the Philippines has some of the highest digital service prices and relatively slower internet speeds within the Asia Pacific region (Quimba & Calizo, 2018). The World Bank (2024) reported that fixed and mobile broadband in the Philippines accounted for over 11% and 2% of its gross national income (GNI), respectively, one to two times higher than the average costs in other ASEAN countries. Additionally, despite the high costs, the median download speeds for fixed and mobile broadband in the Philippines, at 92 Mbps and 28 Mbps, respectively, fall below the ASEAN average.

Furthermore, many businesses have yet to leverage ICTs fully, and there has also been an observed high level of digital skills gap in the workforce that needs to be addressed (AlphaBeta, 2021). According to the World Bank (2020), to improve the state of digitalization in the Philippines, there is a pressing need to upgrade the country's digital infrastructure, especially concerning internet connectivity. Based on

one of the email interviews, service providers generally need more infrastructure for internet connectivity, particularly in remote or far-flung rural areas.

Within the Philippine government, several plans have been developed outlining e-governance and digitalization strategies over the years, such as the National Information Technology Plan for the 21st Century 1992-1998, Philippine ICT Roadmap 2006-2010, Philippine Digital Strategy of 2011-2016, Philippine e-Government Master Plan of 2012, and Philippine Digital Transformation Strategy 2022 (Treceña, 2021). However, institutional challenges persist, hindering the successful implementation of e-governance and digitalization efforts. Magno (2018) highlighted that the government has generally fallen short of investing adequately in digital infrastructure and services. He further pointed out that a significant barrier to e-government in the country is the bureaucratic culture within public institutions, which is averse to risk and resistant to change. Magno also recommended strengthening the demand for open data and policies, as well as engaging universities as knowledge partners in capacity building for chief information officers and research programs to track progress concerning e-government.

In the context of local climate and disaster data management, the importance of ICTs cannot be overstated. These technologies encompass all hardware and software components that interface with and manage information and communication processes (Peansupap & Walker, 2005). Despite its importance, the adoption and use of ICTs for DRR-CCA face challenges in the Philippine LGUs' context. Financial limitations hinder many from acquiring essential ICT equipment and facilities for effective data management in DRR-CCA. For instance, an environmental management officer in Marikina City revealed the city's inability to enhance internet connectivity due to the financial strains of installing a second antenna (Asuncion, 2023). Budget restrictions also impede the regular updating of ICT hardware and software, leading to processing inefficiencies and system crashes. Limited funds also hamper the creation of centralized data repositories, making data gathering and storage challenging (GFDRR, 2016b).

Funding limitations imposed by national policies hinder the utilization of local funds for DRR-CCA, such as acquiring internet services as part of pre-disaster activities. Consequently, LGUs must rely on general fund allocations, constraining their budgetary capacities. Regarding their use of digital technologies, many Philippine LGUs rely on mobile technology, the internet, online social media tools, space-based technologies (remote sensing and satellite communications), and various radios (amateur and satellite) for their disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation operations. However, diffusion levels appear insufficient, given the primary responsibilities assigned to LGUs.

Considering the social aspect of diffusion, the technical capacity to engage with, and the level of acceptance by a community to incorporate digital technology, challenges are evident as well. In the Philippines, survey data reveal that trust in digital services was relatively low (44%) as their trust had been compromised before this (Microsoft Communications Team, 2019), a problem exacerbated by recent public breaches in digital databases (Panti, 2024).

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digital services was relatively low (44%) as their trust had been compromised before this (Microsoft Communications Team, 2019), a problem exacerbated by recent public breaches in digital databases (Panti, 2024). This is particularly concerning given the relatively high number of data breaches that have occurred in the country in recent years. For instance, the Palo Alto Networks (PANW) 2023 State of Cybersecurity ASEAN report noted that the country was hit by the highest number of cyberattacks in Southeast Asia, with 29% of Filipino organizations experiencing a 50% increase in cybersecurity-related incidents (Antivola, 2023). Within the public sector, the National Intelligence Coordinating Agency (NICA) has already reported over 200 data breaches in 'high-level' government agencies less than halfway through 2025 (Bordey, 2025).

This can be further compounded by the risk of ICT systems themselves being damaged during disasters, potentially resulting in data loss. Additionally, when disasters render ICT infrastructure damaged or unreliable, reliance on alternative methods with unsecured properties can pose additional risks to data security (Alvarez et al., 2016). These, among others, can affect the extent to which people and institutions trust the data security and privacy of digital technologies, which in turn influences acceptance and the overall level of digital technology diffusion (Oesterreich et al., 2024). These underscore the need for institutionalizing policies, programs, and other measures to protect and ensure the robustness of ICT systems—such as the Critical Information Infrastructure Protection Act now being proposed for national legislation—and for strengthening systems or platforms for protecting ICT infrastructure, such as the National Asset Registry System (NARS), which generally facilitates the development of a comprehensive inventory of the government's non-financial assets and may include infrastructure relevant to ICT systems such as telecommunications towers (Abasola, 2023; Bureau of the Treasury, 2024).

Standards for Data Management

Achieving the desired results for effective local data management proves challenging in the Philippines due to the need for standardized data management procedures. Inconsistent data collection and storage contribute to duplicated efforts and inefficient data gathering. A UNDP study (2022a) highlighted how the need for a unified framework for data access resulted in fundamental issues, such as multiple digital platforms displaying the same data, causing fragmented data exchange among stakeholders. This problem also hampers LGUs in efficiently and effectively managing and sharing data with other government institutions and the general public for coordination and collaboration purposes, as shared in one of the email interviews. Furthermore, it was revealed that these challenges lead to administrative inefficiencies due to the need for standardized software applications and the varying personnel capacities in utilizing these digital platforms.

The UNDP (2022a) report also reveals non-standardized data formats across agencies, and without uniform practices, the fragmentation of data across different actors also hinders efficient coordination and decision-making. As a result, many national government agencies and LGUs in the Philippines need more clarity in managing and maintaining exposure databases, including the frequency of necessary data updates and processing of scientifically sound assessments. One of the email interviews also highlighted this issue, stating that in the conduct of comprehensive risk assessments, for example, the development of datasets is distributed across

various government agencies, resulting in conflicting guidance provided to local governments when forming and extracting pertinent databases and results. Nonetheless, it was also mentioned that the national government is already trying to address this concern on data standardization through their GeoRiskPH initiative involving several government agencies.

Accurate documentation and data organization are crucial for readily available analysis, enabling the identification of patterns and trends essential for informed decision-making. Comprehensive information assists governments, organizations, and communities in assessing vulnerabilities, mitigating risks, and developing appropriate response strategies. However, the KIIs suggest that not all recommendations are implemented by city governments due to various political, social, and financial considerations. As one of the key informants said:

As much as the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO) is very keen, our recommendation to remove people from the hazard zone is not as easy as that. There are many things to be considered—politically, socially, and everything. It also entails a huge financial requirement on the local government's part.

This suggests that standardization in data management should not only cover the aspects of data collection, processing, and analysis but should also extend to how data is utilized in decision-making.

It is important to note that the national government's development and imposition of standards on LGUs do not infringe on their local autonomy. Rather, they are intended to guide and ensure integration, consistency, efficiency, and effectiveness in data management, ultimately mitigating climate and disaster risks. As expressed in one of the email interviews:

While it is true that local governments have the autonomy to prepare their developmental plans and possess a deeper understanding of their needs and issues, national government agencies must ensure the alignment of mainstreaming disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation, particularly in integrating data management.

Digital Divide

The digital divide refers to inequalities in access and use of information and communications technologies. This concept is also related to the previously discussed driving force on the level of digital technology diffusion. However, the digital divide generally emphasizes the disparities in adoption and utilization between people and institutions. The literature on digital divides is vast, with discrepancies in opinions and results. The discrepancy arises due to the digital divide's dynamic, changing, and multidimensional nature, requiring an analysis to consider several variables, technologies, and territories. Some scholars have noted that at least three levels of digital divides exist: first-level referring to a lack of access and equipment, second level referring to differences in the effective use of digital technology and "e-skills," and third level about the ability to convert digital gains into offline outcomes (Aissaoui, 2022, pp. 689–690). Studies have shown that digital divides also pervade within nations owing to differential developments among localities (e.g., Gladkova et al., 2020 in Russia; Okai, 2022 in India; Quang & Thanh, 2023 in Vietnam).

Digital divides have led to uneven practices across different contexts. For instance, UN Assistant Secretary General and Director of the UNDP Crisis Bureau, Asako Okai, asks if women and children are fourteen times more likely than men to die when disasters strike, why are responses too often still gender-blind (Okai, 2022). Disasters magnify existing gender inequalities, yet the development of DRR-CCA policies, strategies, and initiatives often excludes women. Making ICTs more accessible, in this case, would not only lessen a digital gender divide, allowing women to better respond in times of disaster, but would also allow policymakers to address gender-differentiated impacts of disasters and build more sustainable and resilient communities (Deen, 2022). Divides arising from differing governance approaches, compounded by barriers in transferring public information and practices, have led to delays in immediate and long-term planning and a lack of citizen participation in Vietnam (Quang & Thanh, 2023).

In the Philippines, multidimensional barriers hinder the use of digital tools, such as over-generalizing technologies and their implementation. Many of the email interviews also reaffirm the existence of the digital divide; one even mentioned that the “digital divide typically exists between urban and rural areas and that not all citizens have access to information and communications technologies.” According to the World Bank (2024), household internet penetration for fixed broadband stands at only around 33%, with the National Capital Region being the sole market where over 30% of households have access to fixed wired broadband. In two-thirds of all provinces, constituting 36% of the national population, the reach of fixed wired broadband is less than 10%. Further illustrating the digital divide between urban and rural areas in the country, the World Bank estimated that in rural areas, progress in household internet penetration over the last 10 years has been only one-third of the progress made in urban centers.

As discussed in the email interviews, it is essential to emphasize that the digital divide is not only about limitations in terms of availability and accessibility but also about the capabilities of people and institutions to use and maximize the use of these digital platforms. Nevertheless, low levels of digital literacy remain a major challenge in the Philippines. The World Bank (2024) also reported that in the Philippines, only 2% of youth and adults can use basic arithmetic formulas in Excel, 6% can copy and paste in a document, and 7% can attach a file to an email. These findings underscore the necessity of integrating digital skills more comprehensively into the country’s education system. Even if digital services and technologies are readily available, individuals’ limited digital skills can considerably hinder their adoption and effective use.

At the meso level, the digital divide is likewise apparent. HUCs with relatively higher incomes are generally in a better position to invest in digital projects that strengthen data management. For example, Baguio City’s Barangay Digital Twin Project developed digital representations of its barangays, providing data on land cover, building occupancy, density, and disaster risk (Refuerzo, n.d.). Quezon City, under its drainage master plan, installed flood sensors and rain gauges through the internet of things (IoT) to support real-time monitoring (Quezon City, 2024). Pasig City has also built a network of ICT systems—including GIS, surveillance cameras, centralized audio systems, public alarm systems, and early warning tools—for an integrated disaster emergency management and sustainable development (United

Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change [UNFCCC], 2023). In contrast, similar digital initiatives are more difficult to implement in rural areas, not only because of resource constraints per se but also due to inadequate ICT infrastructure and poor access to reliable internet connectivity (Seráfica et al., 2023).

A lack of recognition of the contexts in which local governments and other institutions introduce technologies has also resulted in widening digital divides rather than closing them (Thinking Machine Data Science [TMDS], 2022). Although the literature clearly shows that contexts experiencing digital divides have reduced capacity to conduct disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation activities, the possibilities for improving the situation are also abundant. A nuanced adoption that acknowledges the multidimensional realities of a particular context, of cross-comparative research findings into policymaking, is one prominent way of addressing gaps in digital divides.

Emerging Technologies

Advancements in technology and the capacity-building of government workers have unlocked the potential to enhance public practices. Modern technologies offer capabilities and applications that can revolutionize the horizon of local climate and disaster data management. In the Philippines, the national government conducted training programs on ICTs for disaster risk reduction, climate change, green growth, and sustainable development (Department of Information and Communications Technologies [DICT], 2019, p. 33). In practice, many national government agencies in the country have also begun using social media as a means of announcing content for disaster management (DICT, 2019, p. 28), with its practice having been described as in a state of “constructive chaos” —where each unit has its norms and practices in their conduct of social media use (Alampay et al., 2018, p. 188).

The emergence of new technologies applied to disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation has caused a re-evaluation of how relevant practices and information can be improved. Blockchain, a decentralized way of managing and storing data, reduces the risk of losing data, which is centralized within data centers, during natural disasters. Though a cheaper alternative in cloud storage exists, blockchain technology promises better security in safeguarding such data (Roundy, 2023), a salient concern in the Philippines, given that several national government websites have been hacked and public databases stolen (Chi, 2023).

Some experiments, such as in a pilot case in China, have also explored how deploying AI in the public sector can create value in data integration, policy innovation, smart applications, and collaboration (Li et al., 2023). Some researchers have tried employing a convolutional neural network (i.e., DenseNet201), a type of network that flows from inputs to output in one direction, to make disaster damage assessments in structures a faster process (Abadicio et al., 2023). South Korea, on the other hand, has invested USD170 million in pursuing metaverse technology, hoping to reap benefits by creating economic, social, and cultural value, despite citizen criticisms of both the feasibility of the impacts and the vision of its use as articulated by the government (Park, 2022).

The literature on emerging technologies and how these will affect disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation is still unfolding. Different considerations, such as the affordability of the technology in contrast to existing alternatives (e.g.,

nuclear vs. electric vs. fossil fuel), the time it takes to develop and implement these, and the capacity of a particular context to adopt these technologies, all interconnect and create several feasible directions as to where the policies and practices in the Philippines will be 10 to 15 years from now.

Scenario Development

The five driving forces—*institutional capacity, level of digital technology diffusion, standards for data management, digital divide, and emerging technologies*—serve as dimensions for developing future potential scenarios by the year 2050. Dator's (2009) scenario archetypes—*continued growth, collapse, discipline, and transformation*—define the scenarios and their respective characteristics. After iterating on these four archetypal narratives, the researchers synthesized the most desirable elements into a single preferred scenario, which blends the dynamism of *transformation*, the stability of *continued growth*, the equity safeguards of *discipline*, and the cautionary lessons of *collapse*. The different scenarios, refined and validated through email interviews, are described in succeeding discussions.

Treading Water (Continued Growth)

“The current trajectory of development will continue, roughly at the same pace and in the same direction as until now” (Dator, 2009, as cited in Barandon et al., 2021, p. 42).

- Institutional capacity: Institutional capacities of LGUs have generally improved, but attracting qualified specialists remains a major challenge.
- Level of digital technology diffusion: Urban and high-income LGUs can invest and improve their ICT infrastructure, while rural and low-income local governments struggle with limited resources.
- Standards for data management: Data management practices across LGUs remain unstandardized and unpredictable.
- Digital divide: There remains a disparity between urban and rural populations regarding internet penetration and levels of digitalization, including technological access and digital literacy.
- Emerging technologies: Emerging technologies are integrated into capacity-building programs, yet their applications are limited to small-scale prototypes and test implementations.

As the Philippines continues to face challenges from natural hazards and disaster incidents, LGUs are working to enhance their data management practices for DRR-CCA. While there have been some improvements through advanced and emerging ICTs, these advancements remain largely unstandardized and unpredictable. High-income and urban LGUs, often supported by international or interlocal partnerships, have a greater capacity to develop DRR-CCA practices. These efforts typically focus on creating more resilient urban infrastructure through preventative programs and data practices. In contrast, low-income and rural LGUs often rely on local resources, leading to band-aid solutions and ad-hoc adjustments to improve disaster response capabilities. Consequently, the digital divide between urban and rural areas remains a persistent challenge.

Capacity-building efforts for LGUs are increasingly influenced by buzzwords from consultants, such as blockchain, data integration, policy innovation, innovative applications, AI-driven collaborations, and faster disaster damage assessment through convolutional neural networks (e.g., DenseNet201). Although small-scale prototypes and test implementations of these technologies are occasionally seen, local data management practices remain unchanged. Furthermore, rural and impoverished LGUs struggle to attract qualified talent due to low salaries and limited financial capacity to regularize personnel. In some cases, individuals with unrelated graduate degrees are placed in key positions simply because they are the only candidates who meet the minimum qualifications on paper.

Sinking to New Depths (Collapse)

“Due to unforeseen external causes or an internal implosion, the current system will regress to a lower level of development” (Dator, 2009, as cited in Barandon et al., 2021, p. 42).

- Institutional capacity: Inadequate organizational and human resource capabilities pose challenges for LGUs in effectively managing local climate and disaster data.
- Level of digital technology diffusion: Severe budget constraints further impede local governments from investing in key ICT infrastructure for improved data management.
- Standards for data management: The government’s climate and disaster data has become fragmented and idiosyncratic, with national databases increasingly unreliable and outdated.
- Digital divide: The digital access and literacy gap has widened substantially, particularly between urban and rural populations. On a global scale, the Philippines also lags significantly behind other countries, especially among its ASEAN neighbors.
- Emerging technologies: The application of emerging technologies in government remains overly academic and far-fetched, given the country’s generally poor state of technological use and adoption.

Driven mainly by socioeconomic factors, most Filipinos have lost confidence in the Philippine government. Many highly skilled and capable individuals, who could strengthen DRR-CCA in the country, have sought to immigrate to protect themselves and their families from financial ruin. Those who remain in positions where they can affect meaningful change have either retired, increased their consultancy fees due to the premium value of their knowledge, or filled positions simply because they were the only available candidates. In areas that have retained a sizeable workforce, a shortage of capable personnel has dramatically slowed disaster response times, and the reduced number of skilled workers has made disaster response efforts more risky. Climate and disaster data management has become fragmented and inconsistent, as national databases have become unreliable and outdated.

Inadequate organizational and human resource capabilities hinder LGUs from efficiently managing climate and disaster data. Despite passing pertinent laws, many LGUs still lack an office or unit to manage these concerns. Additionally, they often

lack focal persons to address related issues and coordinate initiatives, making it more difficult for LGUs to secure national or non-government organizations' funding. Severe budget constraints further impede LGUs from investing in key ICT infrastructure, worsening the digital divide, particularly between urban and rural populations. On a global scale, the Philippines lags significantly behind other countries, especially its ASEAN neighbors. While many nations already benefit from advanced technologies in the public sector, these remain a distant dream in the Philippines, given the country's generally poor technological adoption.

Navigating the Currents (Discipline)

“Continued growth will be either undesirable or unsustainable long term, leading the society to organize itself around a set of overarching values or principles to exercise constraint” (Dator, 2009, as cited in Barandon et al., 2021, p. 42).

- Institutional capacity: To attract specialists, qualification standards have been relaxed, and salary schedules have been enhanced. However, the government requires them to undergo regular training or continue professional education.
- Level of digital technology diffusion: Excessive control and regulatory policies limit technological growth.
- Standards for data management: Standards and decision-making processes, including data management, are highly centralized and closely regulated by the national government.
- Digital divide: Due to the slow progress in technological growth, the digital divide remains a problem, particularly in rural and low-income areas that struggle to comply with stringent regulations.
- Emerging technologies: The government has implemented stringent regulations in response to the unintended consequences of using emerging technologies.

Due to technological threats related to cybersecurity, the spread of misinformation, and data privacy, the Philippine government has shifted its data management policies towards increased centralization. Consequently, online platforms and digital tools have been highly regulated through guidelines, standards, and decision-making processes concerning public data collection, processing, and analysis. This has resulted in LGUs relying on the national government for their data needs, including those related to DRR-CCA, making relevant administrative processes inefficient. Although there has been a high degree of standardization in data management practices, excessive government control and regulatory policies have disincentivized technological investments and overall growth in the country. As a result, the digital divide remains a challenge, with rural and low-income areas struggling to meet the procedural, technical, and other requirements to comply with the stringent national regulations regarding digital tools.

To address human resource problems, the government has dramatically reduced the emigration of highly skilled individuals and has even offered government stipends and temporary waivers of civil service requirements to encourage more individuals

to take up LGU posts, particularly in rural areas. To address pay differences and lost opportunities due to emigration, the government promises to undertake several institutional changes in the future, but only if citizens and government workers demonstrate the political will to see these changes through, effectively shifting the burden of discipline onto the population. Furthermore, while qualification standards have been relaxed and salary schedules enhanced, the government has instituted a policy requiring LGU personnel to undergo regular training or continue professional education.

Charting New Waters (Transformation)

“Current behavior, beliefs, or norms will evolve or be replaced by new norms to address some of today’s challenges. This is often imagined to be achieved through high-tech developments or spiritual transformation” (Dator, 2009, as cited in Barandon et al., 2021, p. 42).

- **Institutional capacity:** While the number of people with competencies in emerging technologies, such as AI and blockchain, has grown, the government cannot keep pace with the private sector hiring such talents.
- **Level of digital technology diffusion:** The rapid growth in the use and adoption of advanced technologies in the Philippines has become inevitable, driven by the prevalence of technological advancements and relevant policies from developed nations.
- **Standards for data management:** Due to a lack of standardization and regulatory policies, technologies are in a state of “constructive chaos,” leading to negative consequences.
- **Digital divide:** Although improvements have been made to reduce the gap in the adoption and use of digital tools, there remains a significant disparity between urban and rural areas in terms of maximizing these tools.
- **Emerging technologies:** Many national government agencies and LGUs have begun using advanced technologies, but the usage level varies greatly depending on institutional capacities.

With the rapid advancement of technology and policies from developed nations, the Philippines faces an inevitable need to adopt disruptive technologies for constructive purposes. This shift is driven by various citizen-involved disaster management practices facilitated through ICT. Despite the country’s limited technical capacity, the adoption of these technologies continues, albeit with challenges. While there has been growth in the number of people with the skills to use emerging technologies, the government struggles to match the private sector in hiring such talent and implementing the necessary policies for technology use. Consequently, LGUs are unable to leverage these advanced technologies fully. Moreover, despite progress in reducing the digital tool adoption gap, significant disparities remain between urban and rural areas.

Entrepreneurial corporations and individuals, noticing the lack of standardization in new technology use, are developing private solutions and innovations to address these gaps. This situation creates constructive chaos, where no one has yet mastered the best way to integrate new tools into existing practices. Each

new disaster presents opportunities and challenges, prompting ongoing learning and adaptation among public servants, non-governmental organizations, and individuals as they become more familiar with these advancements. The continuous emergence of new technologies and startups in both social and traditional media has led to unregulated technology use and unintended consequences due to the rapid pace of adoption.

Resilient and Transformative Local DRR-CCA (Preferred Scenario)

In 2050, every Philippine LGU operates within a seamlessly interconnected, citizen-centered data ecosystem that delivers anticipatory, equitable, and innovation-driven disaster risk governance. Ubiquitous sensor networks and low-orbit satellites stream climate, geospatial, and socioeconomic data into interoperable LGU data meshes that federate, through a quantum-secure national resilience ledger, into a real-time digital twin of the archipelago. Universal 6G/terahertz connectivity and edge-cloud computing eliminate the urban–rural digital divide, providing even the most remote barangays with millisecond-speed analytics and immersive decision dashboards.

Professionalized DRR-CCA offices house AI co-labs that transform continuous data flows into hyper-local early warning services, adaptive scenario models, and tokenized incentive markets rewarding citizen-led resilience innovations. A harmonized standards regime and zero-trust cybersecurity architecture safeguard privacy while enabling friction-free data sharing among government, academia, civil society, and the private sector. Every household, school, and micro-enterprise remains digitally ready through nationwide broadband, embedded climate risk curricula, and lifelong upskilling programs. Participatory data trusts enforce inclusive design norms, ensuring that advanced technologies—artificial intelligence, distributed ledgers, and extended reality training—amplify social equity and environmental stewardship.

This governance landscape couples exponential technological capability with disciplined safeguards and sustained capacity building, producing LGUs that serve as adaptive, transparent, and trusted stewards of community well-being amid accelerating climatic and socioeconomic change, ultimately realizing the resilient and transformative future envisioned for the Philippines in 2050.

Setting Goals and Strategies

The developed scenarios offered holistic views of potential futures and served as references for setting goals and strategies across the five dimensions/driving forces. The goals and strategies aim to enhance the institutional capacities of LGUs for climate and disaster data management while improving technological diffusion at the local level. Regarding institutional capacities, the primary objective is to ensure that LGUs possess adequate organizational structures and staffing complements. This will be facilitated, among others, through capacity building and implementing clear and well-defined policies and guidelines. Technological diffusion can be achieved by enabling institutional policy and technical environment, and integrating digital technologies into policies and guidelines related to DRR-CCA. These guidelines should incorporate advanced technologies such as AI, blockchain, and the metaverse. In line with these objectives, general goals and corresponding strategies are outlined below, aligning with the five critical forces discussed to assist LGUs in preparing

for the identified scenarios. The research team initially developed the goals and strategies, then validated and finalized them through email interviews. These broad goals and strategies are outlined in the discussions that follow.

Goal 1: LGUs have specialized DRR-CCA departments/offices with skilled and proficient personnel capable of efficiently collecting, processing, and analyzing relevant data to carry out their functions effectively.

Strategies:

- Review and adjust the qualification standards and salary schedules.
- Consider asymmetrical configurations in assigning DRR-CCA responsibilities.
- Establish a regional coordinating body and local departments/offices for climate change-related programs, projects, and activities.

Goal 2: An institutional policy and technical environment enables the adoption and utilization of ICTs for efficient data management, particularly at the local level.

Strategies:

- Integrate ICT adoption and utilization into existing systems for performing LGU functions.
- Review and adjust the allowable expenses for financial obligations, ensuring that they cover the procurement of essential technological tools.
- Establish standardized and interoperable data repositories and systems.

Goal 3: Clear policies with well-defined guidelines are in place and strictly adhered to, standardizing data management practices for LGUs, thus ensuring secure and efficient data utilization.

Strategies:

- Establish a standardized methodology for formulating and harmonizing DRR-CCA plans, including programs, projects, and activities.
- Install firewalls, encryption techniques, and secure networks to safeguard private and sensitive data.
- Foster a culture of data-driven decision-making by educating and training employees to understand the value of data and promote data literacy.

Goal 4: Nearly every household, civil society organization, and private entity, as well as LGUs and national government agencies, should have access to digital platforms and technologies and a sufficient level of digital literacy and readiness.

Strategies:

- Invest in broadband and internet infrastructure to ensure affordable, accessible, and reliable internet access across all areas in the country.
- Mainstream DRR-CCA into the Philippine education system.

- Conduct community-wide training and skill-building initiatives to improve digital literacy and competency.

Goal 5: LGUs are incorporating emerging technologies like AI, blockchain, and the metaverse into various aspects of climate and disaster data management, thus reshaping policy and institutional frameworks at the grassroots level. This will effectively mitigate the impacts of disasters and climate change.

Strategies:

- Allocate resources for critical infrastructure and advancing research and development to support integrating and utilizing emerging technologies.
- Invest in capacity-building for cutting-edge analytic methods.
- Promote alternative funding sources.

Conclusion

Employing a futures and foresight approach, this research crafted various scenarios for the future of local climate and disaster data management in the Philippines. By applying a modified Schwartz's scenario-building process and Dator's scenario archetypes, the research team consolidated a broad range of both known and emerging drivers that can influence local climate and disaster data management. This process enabled the identification of possible interconnections among these factors and the development of four potential future scenarios. From these archetypes, the team also distilled a concise preferred vision—the *Resilient-Transformative Local DRR-CCA 2050*—in which every LGU operates a skilled DRR-CCA office, streams real-time sensor data into quantum-secure ledgers, and leverages AI analytics on universal 6G connectivity. Importantly, the futures methods facilitated the formulation of objectives that can provide a productive foundation for informed decision-making, which policymakers can use to work toward a preferred outcome.

Given the broad scope of this inquiry, the scenarios presented in this research provide a general outlook for the Philippines as a whole rather than focusing on the specific context of individual LGUs. If they wish to better adapt these methods to their particular circumstances, conducting more focused case studies or comparative case studies across different localities could be beneficial. Additionally, future comparative research could focus on social, political, and economic situations at a global or regional scale, such as within ASEAN.

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